

Multiphysics and Mesoscale Modeling of Marine Energy Composites

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ABSTRACT

Characterization of marine energy-based composites has historically been sequentially performed under three primary conditions: dry, completely saturated, or partially saturated. In these environments, diffusive and mechanical properties are often determined separately. While beneficial in understanding baseline material properties, the combined diffusion-mechanical effects under representative loading conditions are not well understood, particularly for marine energy-based systems composed of complicated geometries.

In this work, we aim to develop a finite element model at the mesoscale (i.e., tow length scale) to predict mass uptake, stiffness and strength, under stress free and stressed loading conditions for glass-based fiber reinforced composites (FRCs). Mesoscale modeling is performed to understand the influence of constituent properties (e.g., individual fibers and enveloping resin) on both moisture uptake and mechanical properties. A complete understanding of the property-performance relationship is imperative for design optimization of existing or future full-scale systems. Micromechanical models will be used in conjunction with the mesoscale models to analyze effective tow properties under varying property ranges and volume fractions. The model developed in this work leverages a two-way coupling on the conservation of chemical species and Fick's law of diffusion with conservation of momentum governing equations to resolve the combined effects of moisture absorption on hygroscopic expansion and stress/strain concentrations. Early studies on the influence of stress on diffusion coefficients have been performed with the development of analytical expressions to predict diffusion. These predictions, however, are primarily limited to thin unidirectional composites composed of ideal geometries. This work seeks to build upon an existing mesoscale model of glass-based FRCs by incorporating stress-dependent diffusion coefficients and prediction of degraded strength properties as a function of moisture absorption into the finite element model. Initial simulation results applied to an as-manufactured, image-based geometry that was limited to the linear elastic regime with no additional applied loading demonstrated the diffusivity of the resin within glass-based FRC increased by about 2% on average at final saturation. This percent change corresponded well with the volume change of the resin as expected, which also increased by about 2%. While this increase is small for the stress-free case, further investigation is needed to determine the change in diffusivity under representative environmental loading conditions. Understanding the margins of uncertainty for strength due to these factors will ultimately be valuable in predicting the probability of failure in long term design analysis of marine based systems.

SNL is managed and operated by NTESS under DOE NNSA contract DE-NA0003525